

Ormedian Research Institute

**A CRITICAL STUDY OF OBJECT TRACKING
ALGORITHMS, WITH IMPLEMENTATION OF OBJECT
TRACKER USING OpenCV DNN MODEL WITH
YOLOv4**

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April 17, 2023.

ABSTRACT

Object tracking is a significant concept in the modern world of technology particularly in several computer vision applications. Object to be tracked could be a human, a product, a head, a face, a crowd, player in a sport, vehicles, pedestrians etc. Object tracking algorithm specifically deals with the application of the deep learning principles to first detect objects, apply some set of unique identification to initially detected objects and then track such detected objects as they move from frame to frame in the video with a high accuracy. As it has become very important to leverage the use of technological tools to track the objects in scenes so as to obtain some useful information or suspicious activities in some events for such reasons, object tracking software is now employed in different areas of life so as to provide some levels of systems control and security. Object tracking methods and their underlying ideas will be critically described in this paper. Also, this paper will focus on providing the background study of object tracking, its algorithms, factors affecting the effective performance of object tracking algorithm and then operation of object tracking will be demonstrated with OpenCV Deep Neural Network (DNN) model with a pre-trained YOLO v4 object detection module to derive some experimental results with visual representation of how object tracking algorithm works.

Keywords: Object tracking, DNN Model, YOLO, OpenCV, MOT, SOT, CNN

TABLE OF CONTENT

CONTENT	Page
Title Page	i
Abstract	ii
Table of Content	iii
List of Figures	iv

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background of the Study	1
1.2 Types of Object Tracking	2
1.3 Levels of Object Tracking	3
1.4 Principle of Operation of Object Tracking	3
1.5 Some Existing Object Tracking Algorithm	4
1.6 Factors Affecting Object Tracker	6

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW	8
2.1 Overview of the Chapter	8
2.2 Related Work Reviewed	8

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 IMPLEMENTATION	11
3.1 Methodology	11
3.1.1 Simplest Block Diagram of Object Tracking	11
3.1.2 Why YOLOv4 for Detection	11
3.1.3 Why OpenCV for Object Tracking	12
3.1.4 Steps Required for the Tracking Process	12
3.1.5 Object Tracking Algorithm Flowchart	13

3.2	Results	14
3.3	Discussions	16

CONCLUSION

REFERNCES

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 3.1: Block Diagram of the Object Tracking Working Process	11
Figure 3.2: Flowchart of the Object Tracker	13
Figure 3.3: Object Detection before Tracking	14
Figure 3.4: Output of the Tracking Algorithm on Moving Cars	14
Figure 3.5: Output of the Tracking Algorithm on Moving Birds in the First Frame	15
Figure 3.6: Output of the Tracking Algorithm on Moving Birds in the Second Frame	15
Figure 3.7: Output of the Tracking Algorithm on Moving Players (Persons)	16

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Researches in the recent years have shown that deep-learning algorithms have continued to offer numerous solutions different real-life problems. With computer vision as a trending field, deep learning application in object tracking continues to evolve in different dimensions with advanced algorithms being presented by different researchers as day passes by. Object tracking is used for a wide variety of applications especially in the areas where different types of input sources are images, videos, pre-recorded video, or real time video. Object tracking algorithms are tailored towards the input needed to ensure that the accurate output is produced. Several algorithms of object tracking that have been developed resolved to the same task of detecting, identifying, and interpreting objects in a video as a set of trajectories with a high degree of accuracy. With different object tracking algorithms in existence, those built on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) are considered the most used and reliable network because of their capability to perform with great accuracy if carefully designed. Although there are several other popular architectures and algorithms used for object tracking some of which are: Generative Adversarial Network (GAN), Siamese Neural Network (SNNs), Autoencoders (AEs), Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), custom neural network, Fast R-CNN, Faster R-CNN and their variants. For trackers to work as expected, the algorithm must be carefully designed to be free from errors so that the tracker can remain accurate over different frames in the video. As essential as object tracking is, object detection also serves an important role in the tracking process because it relies on worldly information register that helps to significantly reduce false detection. Object detection technique employed in the tracking system are of different varieties and the developer of the tracking algorithm may decide to choose any of the techniques.

Object tracking as a concept has become the topic of immense interest in the domain of technology today due to the fact that there is a lot of information about objects present in a video as frame changes with time. Hence, object tracking has had its implications in diverse areas such as in security system, video surveillance, medical equipment, transportation, military, and some other

industries. With increase in the level of technology, it is believed that research possibilities in the area of object tracking is numerous. Computer vision and deep learning projects now employ method of video tracking in real-time applications.

1.2 TYPES OF OBJECT TRACKING

Object tracking has evolved in different kinds and they all take into consideration two different components i.e. target representation and localization. The commonly known categories are image tracking, visual tracking, object tracking cameras, and video tracking.

- A. *Object Tracking Camera:*** This is one of the simplest types of object tracking. It performs object tracking task through video feed of a USB supported camera or IP camera. This type of tracking is mostly chosen for real-time video streams.
- B. *Image Tracking:*** This is the process of scanning an image, detecting, and locating objects available in a photo. It is a feature of augmented reality that makes it possible for applications to detect 2-dimensional images after predetermining the image target by allowing augmented digital content to appear as animations, slideshow, videos, etc. Image tracker could have a single or multiple target functionality which will enable the tracking of one or more images to be possible at a time.
- C. *Visual Tracking:*** This is regarded as the type of object tracking in which future position of an object is estimated. i.e., it gives information about where an object will eventually be located. Principle of visual tracking is now employed in surveillance cameras and driverless cars.
- D. *Video Tracking:*** In computer vision, video tracking deals with the process of locating moving objects with respect to time by using camera. It is a complex process due to the fact that there is a need for objects available in the video frame to be detected and recognized before the tracking can be initiated. Hence, it is a time-consuming task. Industries of different kinds now leverage the use of video tracking principles in real-life applications. Possible areas of use of video tracking are in video editing, augmented reality, traffic control, human-computer interaction, medical imaging, video communication and compression, security and surveillance. In computer vision applications today, video tracking is considered as the most popular kind of object tracking. It works by first

determining the coordinates of the target object, and then uses the spatial and temporal information to estimate the position of a target object in each consecutive frame of the video.

1.3 LEVELS OF OBJECT TRACKING

Object tracking is further classified into two different types based on the nature of the object to be tracked. The two classes are Single Object Tracking (SOT) and Multiple Object Tracking (MOT). The objective of the **SOT** is to scan the video and track a specific target throughout the video span. It achieves this by drawing bounding box around such a target object if found in the video frame and then locates the same object wherever it exists in the rest of the video frame. SOT is the choice of most industries when the primary focus is mainly on one unique object in the entire frames of a video. **MOT** on the other hand is a complex type of object tracking based on the fact that it aims at detecting and tracking multiple objects in a video. Be it SOT or MOT, the goal of every object tracker is to carefully identify and locate target objects (i.e. objects of interest) in each frame of the video and then associate such identified objects across the rest of the video frames to keep track of their movement within these frames over time.

1.4 PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION OF OBJECT TRACKING

Systematic operations of object tracking is generally well-defined in all cases, starting from selection of the target objects, tracking of such objects, and finally retain the classes of those objects in space and over time. But before the aforementioned procedures could be successfully put in place for object position to be estimated and other relevant information obtained from the video the following processes listed below must be undergone.

- (1) ***Specifying the input data:*** This is the very first step required in object tracking. Pre-recorded video data or real-time video obtained from the camera could be used as input data and it is from this input video that objects of choice can be detected and tracked. This step is very essential because without it, there would be nothing to read or track. Computer vision tool like the OpenCV is very useful in this very step for preprocessing the input data.

- (2) **Detection of object:** since there is a need for bounding box to be drawn around target objects in the video to show that an object has been detected, object detection algorithm that gives the best accuracy has to be chosen in this case to ensure that false detection is completely minimized.
- (3) **Labelling/ID assignment:** this is the next stage after detection, the tracking algorithm is configured to assign a unique identification label to each uniquely identified object. Such a unique object could be a car or a person or any other target object available in the video being read as an input.
- (4) **Tracking of detected and identified objects:** This is the final step of the object tracking, the detected and identified objects are kept track by simply storing their relevant path information as they move from frame to frame in the video.

1.5 SOME EXISTING OBJECT TRACKING ALGORITHMS

Object tracking algorithms almost all work nearly the same way but may vary with their capability in terms of additional feature they offer. List of some common object detection algorithm is given below:

- (i) **SORT:** short for Simple Online Real Time Tracking (SORT) was published by Bewley et al in 2017, it belongs to the category of the first algorithms developed to handle object tracking task in real-time projects. SORT uses Faster Region CNN for object detection, Kalman filter for position estimation, association then follows if predictions and actual detections overlap, and the final step is the creation and deletion of track identities to avoid unbound growth. In SORT algorithm, to link detection to tracking, Intersection Over Union (IOU) is the criterion used. As good as the SORT algorithm is, too many identity switches are created whenever the sight of object is blocked.
- (ii) **FairMOT:** This algorithm was developed to achieve a high level of detection and a better tracking accuracy where multiple objects are to be tracked in a video. The beauty of a good object tracking algorithm is not just to detect and track objects but to re-identify objects correctly after occlusion. This characteristic gives the FairMOT algorithm some overheads when compared to

other object tracking algorithms based on the fact that not all of them have a reliable pipeline for re-identification. To improve tracking accuracy significantly, FairMOT operates on a feature maps of high resolution.

(iii) **DeepSORT:** This is regarded as an extension of the SORT algorithm and it was published by Wojke, Paulus, and Wojke in 2019. DeepSORT algorithm was developed so as to enrich the existing SORT algorithm with more advanced visual features by incorporating deep learning concept into it. DeepSORT has two steps: the first is the cost matrix calculation which is responsible for the assignment of scores based on the track that a given detection belongs to. Second is the assignment problem in which each track with scores below a certain frame threshold. A new detection is automatically assigned by the algorithm so that the detection can have the least cost associated with such a track. IOU matching is run by the algorithm whenever it observes that some tracks do not match.

(iv) **MDNet:** short for Multidomain Network. This is another tracking algorithm considered to be fast and accurate. It is a CNN based algorithm that is inspired by R-CNN to increase the speed and overall efficiency of the algorithm. MDNet algorithm is mostly useful when real-time object tracking is required. It is still very accurate despite the complexity in its computation.

(v) **Object Tracking MATLAB:** MATLAB provides functionalities for performing an automatic detection and tracking of motion objects. The detection is achieved by Gaussian mixture methods whereas foreground masking is used to eliminate possible noise. Kalman filter is used for estimating the motion of tracked objects. MATLAB application in computer vision object tracking is highly relevant especially when multiple objects are to be tracked. The function behind this is the “multiObjectTracker” which makes the tracking of object from frame to frame in videos possible.

(vi) **OpenCV Object Tracking:** OpenCV library in computer vision is an essential tool that makes object tracking easier. OpenCV library has up to 8 object tracking methods and it relies on online learning classifiers. Methodologies involved in using OpenCV for tracking is of different kinds with each of them having their pros and cons. Examples of these methods are Boosting Tracker, Multiple Instance Learning Tracker (MIL), Kernelized correlation Filters (KCF) Tracker, Tracking Learning Detection (TLD) Tracker, MedianFlow Tracker, Generic Object Tracking

Using Regression Network) Tracker, Minimum Output Sum of Squared Error Tracker, Channel and Spatial Reliability of Discriminative Correlation Filter (CSRT) Tracker etc.

1.6 FACTORS AFFECTING THE PERFORMANCE OF OBJECT TRACKER

(1) ***Distractive Backgrounds:*** input data which is to be read for object tracking task must have a clean and clear background. The background of input data be it video or image to train the tracking model can make or mar the accuracy of such a model because unclear or unclean or busy background input sources might make detection of small objects available in frames harder and this will pose a serious challenge on the intended output. Cases where there is background clutter could also affect the accuracy of the output result because it will be very difficult to detect and identify an object that whose colour is the same as that of the background of the video itself.

(2) ***Noise:*** Quality of the camera sensor to be used for acquisition of the video plays a very important role in the tracking accuracy. If the sensor of a camera is of low quality, there is every tendency that there will be some noise in the video signals acquired. Hence, cameras with high quality should always be chosen at all time to ensure that errors that could be generated by camera sensor is insignificant.

(3) ***Occlusion:*** this is another factor affecting the object tracking accuracy. This is a phenomenon whereby some objects in the video file being read fall behind each other thereby making such occluded objects undetectable or making two different occluded objects identified as one. The effect of occlusion is that it could make it harder for object trackers to observe properly the object of interest. This is usually a common phenomenon because overlapping of objects in video scenes can be inevitable. Therefore, the tracking algorithm must be able to handle occlusion problems effectively. Hence, to prevent any form of misidentification in the tracking process, the algorithm to be used must be occlusion sensitive.

(4) ***Object Poses:*** Variation in the appearance of an object could also vary its projection in the frame of the video as the movement of such object changes. This could present such an object as a strange object if the model is not well trained.

(5) **Tracking Speed:** speed at which object can be tracked varies due to the fact that algorithms differ in their way of influencing the tracking process. Hence, it is important that the most accurate object tracking algorithm must be carefully chosen to enhance the detection and tracking ability of the model. Hence, there is a need for faster and accurate tracker. In some computer vision applications of object tracking, fast R-CNN and Faster R-CNN are now being used to boost the speed of most R-CNN networks.

(6) **Illumination:** video scenes are usually affected by variation in the level of illumination and this causes the tracking system to lose its confidence thereby classifying objects incorrectly. Even before object is being tracked, factors such as light reflection or shadow can have a negative impact on the performance of the detection system employed in the object tracker thereby causing the loss of information.

(7) **Scale Variation:** size misconceptions is another barrier in object tracking. Aspect ratios of the actual object to be tracked can confuse that tracking algorithm especially if objects are of variety of sizes and aspect ratios. For a reasons like this, tracking algorithm are configured with more techniques such as feature maps, anchor boxes, feature pyramids, etc. in order to overcome the problems evolving from varying spatial scales.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 OVERVIEW OF THE CHAPTER

In this paper, the theoretical background and fundamentals of object tracking have been discussed. As seen, in the previous chapter, it is imperative that the object-tracking algorithm must be well implemented to predict correctly even when the scenes have occlusions present in them. In the process of finding ways to improve object-tracking algorithms, researchers have been making efforts to develop more accurate and reliable algorithms. Some of the work done previously by researchers to contribute to the success of object-tracking algorithms will be discussed in this chapter.

2.2 RELATED WORK REVIEWED

According to [1], detailed description of object tracking was given. Object tracking in their work was regarded as the terminology used to the position of moving objects as well as tracking these objects as they appear in the frames of the video. Also, the authors in [2] emphasized that tracking method can be classified into three types i.e. kernel, point, and silhouette.

In the work of [3], a semi-automatic object-tracking algorithm was proposed by these authors. In their research, they applied the probabilistic relaxation methods to make object tracking perform effectively and efficiently. Their approach achieves smooth and accurate borders for the tracked objects. Whereas border accuracy largely depends on the appearance of the new object, the video background, and the discriminating power of the selected features.

The authors in [4] suggested probabilistic background model for object tracking, after experimenting their model, simulation result showed that there is a high accuracy in their model when compared to some previously existing algorithms. But further suggestion was made on the need for their algorithm to concentrate on higher speed and better accuracy when tracking objects in video sequence.

According to [5], they suggested a technique which achieves the object tracking goal by combining the motion estimation and background subtraction of video sequence. They are interpolation, identification of object, subtraction of the background, and selection of object. It was suggested that this study needs to concentrate on being sensitive to occlusion.

In the work of [6], they demonstrated object tracking with the use of the Camshift technique. Their approach was successful even in the presence of variation in sizes of objects or illumination. The only demerit of this approach was that video full of occlusion could render such algorithm useless.

In the work [7], tracking of object was carried out by the use of image segmentation approach where the colour intensity of the object to be tracked has to be specified. Object classification in this approach is obtained by minimum distance classifier. The result of this approach proved to be highly efficient. Although, this study needs to still find a way to handle occlusion problems.

In [8], the author suggested an algorithm which will isolate moving objects in video sequence after which he then suggested a rule-based algorithm. It was proven by series of experiments that their algorithm performed very well even in complicated scenarios such as track collision, ceased track, etc.

Another algorithm called Joint Probability Data Association Filter (JPDAF). This is a technique applied when multiple object is to be tracked. According to [9], data association of fixed number of objects is carried out by the JPDAF, but if at some points, there is a change in the number of objects then there is going to be an error. While this algorithm helps in object tracking tasks, the algorithm lacks the capability to handle some cases, for example, when new object enters a scene or when previously tracked object exits a scene. In the process of finding algorithm that offers better tracking capability, another algorithm called Multiple Hypothesis Tracking (MHT) algorithm was found to be free from the drawback faced by the JPDAF. The MHT has good tracking ability and also handles occlusion problems pretty well [10].

According to [11], he proposed Dense Tracking Model (QDTrack) after using Faster RCNN extended with Residual Neural Network (RNN). He also proposed a correlational network called CorrTracker, this tracking algorithm enables information to propagate across data associations.

Deep learning is becoming more popular in the area of object tracking. It was observed that deep learning models could detect but there used to be a problem when targets have to be associated i.e.

to keep track of the possible trajectories of objects of interest [12]. To solve this problem, authors in [13] applied both bottom-up approach and top-down approach to obtain the full track of object. Bounding boxes are determined in the top-down approach while in the bottom-up approach, point trajectories are determined.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE OBJECT

TRACKING ALGORITHM USING OpenCV DNN MODEL with YOLOv4

3.1 METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, object tracking algorithm will be implemented to show what the output looks like. As discussed earlier in chapter 1 and 2, there are several tracking algorithms in existence but here, systematic approach to building an object tracking algorithm will be described, implemented, and results will be visually displayed in the result section of this chapter.

Since object tracking algorithm requires an object detector first to make the task easier, You Only Look Once i.e. YOLOv4 is chosen in this paper to perform the object detection task.

3.1.1 Simplest block diagram of Object Tracking system

Figure 3.1: Block Diagram of the Object Tracking Principle.

3.1.2 Why YOLOv4 for Detection?

Although, there are several other object detection algorithms that are also reliable, but YOLOv4 is chosen in this paper because it is one of the fastest and accurate technique for detecting digital images. YOLOv4 being an advanced deep neural network developed to recognize different kind

of objects in a single envelope. Due to its ability to identify object accurately than some other recognition system, its model will be employed in this paper for the detection/recognition task. Part of our object tracking implementation task. It is generally believed that YOLOv4 is very sharp and efficient that it can detect the 20 Pascal object classes which include: person, sheep, cow, cat, dog, birds, horse, train, bicycle, airplane, car, motorbike, boat, bus, bottle, sofa, tv/monitor, dining table, potted plant, and chair. The real-time videos to be used for experimenting object tracking task in this paper will contain some of the object classes aforementioned above so that the intended tracking algorithm in this paper will be able to track the right object. Only three object classes (Car, Persons, and Birds) will be used in this paper to demonstrate the how accurate the algorithm can track an objects.

3.1.3 Why OpenCV for Object Tracking?

OpenCV is a very well-known tool that aids object tracking task in computer vision and this is due to the fact that it has some inbuilt functionalities specifically designed for object tracking purposes. Some of the object trackers which are by default available in the OpenCV are: MIL, CSRT, MedianFlow, GOTURN, etc. Another reason for choosing OpenCV in this paper is that it makes image processing easy. Since the tracking task will be more focused on images of objects within the video sequence, then OpenCV seems to be the right choice in this case.

3.1.4 Steps required for the tracking process

- [1] Import the following libraries/modules: cv2, numpy, and math
- [2] Load and read the video file frame by frame
- [3] Import the ObjectDetection function from the object detection file (Yolo)
- [4] Load the object detector
- [5] Detect objects on frames
- [6] Draw bounding boxes around objects by using the rectangle method of OpenCV
- [7] Initialize counter for frames

- [8] Get center point of each object
- [9] Create a list to save the midpoint of all detected objects
- [10] Compare the position of the points from the previous frame to the point on the current frame so as to assign a unique id to each box and track them. This is achieved by using the “hypot” function of the python math module. The putText function of the OpenCV is used to place text as IDs on those bounding boxes
- [11] Update IDs as frame passes.

3.1.5 Object Tracking Algorithm Flowchart

Figure 3.2: Flowchart of the Object Tracker.

3.2 RESULTS

Figure 3.3: Object Detection before Tracking.

Figure 3.4: Output of the Tracking Algorithm on Moving Cars.

Figure 3.5: Output of the Tracking Algorithm on Moving Birds in the First Frame.

Figure 3.6: Output of the Tracking Algorithm on Moving Birds in the Second Frame.

Figure 3.7: Output of the Tracking Algorithm on Moving Players (Persons).

3.3 DISCUSSION

Values for the distance between the previous frame and the current frame must be carefully chosen when developing the tracking algorithm so that all boxes can have their own IDs without any box left out. If the distance is not carefully selected, some of the tracked objects will not have IDs associated to them. With the distance well worked out, good matches will certainly be picked out through the scale, orientation, and location with consistency. From the results obtained in the object tracking experiments carried out in this paper, at the end of the test, it could be seen clearly that the algorithm achieved a high degree of accuracy in terms of detection and position estimation. Although one of the unavoidable challenges of trackers is occlusion, the mathematics as well as the configuration underlying this algorithm provides sensitivity for the algorithm to adjust itself when occlusion occurs. Although some other object tracking algorithm with the use of OpenCV applies Kalman filter to handle occlusion issues. Therefore, it can be concluded from the results that the tracking algorithm implemented with OpenCV DNN Model and YOLOv4 object detection yielded accurate results.

CONCLUSION

In computer vision applications today, object detectors and trackers are very important especially where the task involves motion based system in which region of interest is of utmost importance. In this paper the theoretical background, challenges, types, applications, implementation and some other theories of object tracking concept have been discussed. Having tested the algorithm on different videos, accuracy was confirmed. With the usefulness of the algorithm implemented in this paper, the algorithm is better in its speed and does not compromise on performance while it optimizes the performance. Although there are several other better object trackers but some of them are usually complex in their computation.

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